

MEANING ASPECTS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH EDUCATIONAL PROVERBS

Xamrayeva Nilufar Xamidullayevna

Dotsent. Named after Islam Karimov

Tashkent State Technical University

Teacher of the Foreign Languages Department:

mbganikhanova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960692>

Abstract: Focusing on the sociolinguistic features of proverbs, analyzing the linguistic and cultural characteristics of some proverbs in the English and Uzbek languages, the unique national customs of both nations, the expression of the unique national character in the daily lifestyle will be shown. . Basically, by critically analyzing the proverbs of both languages, we will study their differences and try to express the common aspects of their similarities using the necessary sources.

Key words: simile, sociolinguistics, proverb, feature, term, metal, national.

Proverbs as a product of word art can be used literally, figuratively, and both. That's why we come across different forms of artistic and visual media in them. But we also see that in proverbs, simile is rarely used, it is not typical for this genre. If we replace articles with similes, they usually lose their proverbial character. For example, let's say the proverb "Nightingale loves chaman", "Adam loves country like a nightingale loves chaman", "Man loves country" or "If you are a farmer, plow, if you are a Mullah, repeat the proverb like a farmer plows, if you are a Mullah, repeat it." utter nonsense ensues. Recently, we have been faced with cases of using the proverb without taking into account this feature in the pages of the press. For example, the saying "Ustoz is great from your father" is being misused in a great way. In this case, there is no discrimination against the father, in that case the people would not have created the saying that God is pleased with the father. Here there is an exaggeration of respect for the teacher. In addition, there are people who believe that God is the first and only teacher of all mankind. Secondly, if the teacher and the father are equated, the meaning of the proverb changes completely and becomes contrary to the views of the people. True, many variants are typical for proverbs. But this does not mean that the article can be changed at will. Variation also has its own natural laws. When proverbs come in succession, one can seem to contradict the other. In fact, it should not be forgotten that staying has different meanings depending on the situation.

The noblest vengeance is to forgive- lazzatli avf intiqomda yo'q If we translate the English equivalent of this proverb literally, **kechirim so'ramoqlik o'ch olishning eng oliyjanob tomonidir.**

Drink in something with one's mother's milk ona suti bilan kirmagan tana suti bilan kirmas. In this proverb, upbringing is meant, and it is used in the sense that the same child will be born from a moral mother.

One fool makes many- Ahmoq elchi ikki tarafni buzar The meaning of this proverb is that some people convey what they heard from one side wrongly to another person, as a result of which there is a misunderstanding between the two sides.

Civility costs nothing-odob oltindan qimmat; The dignity and respect of a decent person is at a good level among others.

More know Tom Fool than Tom Fool knows-Ahmoqning do'sti ko'p, Piyozning po'sti
A stupid person calls everyone a friend and tells all their secrets, which will eventually lead to a warning.

Short pleasure , long lament-bir nafaslik muhabbat-boshga keltirar ofat

Before doing any work, it is necessary to think about its consequences, because what is done after thinking about it does not lead to evil.

Ginger shall be hot in the mouth-Mazali so'zga quloq charchamas

If we translate the English version literally into Uzbek, the ginger fruit gives a bitter taste when put in the mouth. One's tongue runs before one's wit. A person who can't control himself and his tongue in any situation will be in trouble.

Ko'pni yomonlagan ko'muvsiz qolar.

It is known that our people pay special respect to the dead. No matter how bad they were while they were alive, he refrains from speaking ill of them, even if it is true. And in the proverb, it is expressed that people will come to the grief of such a person unwillingly, even if they do not say it in their language, they will not forget who the person really was. Such a strict judgment describes a special warning situation. Burials that hurt many. Here the meaning is expressed that he will die, he will remain in the eyes of the people. Not a calculated friend. Some people thank a friend for small favors. It's about increasing the volume here. A friend with an account does not change. This proverb expresses the meaning that a friend should not forget the good deeds of a friend and should always remember them. Another characteristic of this collection comes from the use of proverbs in the live process, depending on the situation, that is, some proverbs are repeated on topics without changing the meaning of the verses. This is not something that the compilers came up with to artificially increase the size of the collection. All proverbs in the collection are recorded from the people and are kept in the folklore archive of the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is the exchange of these lines, even in the exchange of words and phrases, that there is a difference in meaning. For example, if the word is about a spendthrift woman, the proverb is used in the form of Limcha Mullah's shor of religion, Bad woman is his shor, and if the word is about a representative of an uneducated religion, it is used in the form of Bad wife's shor of din, Limcha Mullah's shor of religion. In such cases, the main accent usually falls on the second verse. One more comment: Many things have changed in a positive direction due to the independence of our country. In particular, religious values were completely restored. Below we will get acquainted with the use of folk proverbs related to education.

Beshikda tekkan, kafanda ketar

The way a new-born child is brought up, it goes with that way until it is born. Just like the old proverb says, if a person with bad behavior is not trained in this life, he may learn a lesson in the next life. Such proverbs are often used against people who have a negative influence on people in society.

Bola loy-ona kulol

Each of us is born to be raised by our mother. Just as potters make the desired shapes and objects out of clay, we are shaped by the way our mother educates us.

Bola tuqqaniki emas- tarbiyalaganniki

We don't like those who give birth to their child and abandon it, they want to own their child after years. In fact, this proverb can be said to be a continuation of the one mentioned above, because the behavior of a child depends on his upbringing. Maybe the mother who gave birth to him is immoral. But if the mother who raised him is quiet, then the child will be like that.

Bolani so'ksang, beti qotar, Ursang, eti qotar

The thing that parents should pay attention to in raising a child is that they should be careful not to say bad things to the child in any case, because the face of the child who hears abuse becomes hard and he does not speak. Therefore, the education of children is disturbed and they do not even listen to the words of older people. They only do what they know is right.

Bog'ing bo'lsa, qo'ra qil, o'g'ling bo'lsa, mulla qil.

If we can translate this proverb into our lives, fence your garden with a wall so that it is not trampled underfoot, raise your son in such a way that what he says is meaningful and what he does is rewarded. In a word, be a wise, believing person.

Onadan ko'rgan to'n bichar, Otadan ko'rgan o'q yo'nar

What the children do at home, what their parents teach them, they will definitely repeat in the future. If we apply this proverb to the organization of a profession or profession, then the role of parents in children's career choices will be great. Not all parents can be professionals. But they will have the skill to direct their child according to their interests.

Ota g'ayratli bo'lsa, Bola ibratli bolar.

In fact, the role of the father is incomparable in making the child educated and enviable. A child may or may not find a place in society through his upbringing.

Otasi buzuqning biri buzuq, Onasi buzuqning bari buzuq.

Fathers and mothers have a great role in raising moral people for our society. If we dwell on this proverb, fathers, especially mothers, have a great influence on the immorality of their children. The behavior of mothers with a negative character is not lost on their children.

Suv bilan ekin o'sar, Tarbiya bilan odam.

It is not an exaggeration to say that the role of proper upbringing in the formation of a person as a human being is just as the role of water is Benazir in the growth of a plant and the fruiting of plants.i.

Terakka qarab, tol o'sar. Onaga qarab, qiz o'sar

A girl learns from her mother. The child of a wise and Muslim mother will surely grow up as a child. Because he will return the things he saw from his mother in his little life. In conclusion, it is worth noting that we can learn about the culture of each nation through folk oral creativity, proverbs, sayings and wise words. In this regard, our second chapter was about paremiology and the occurrence of proverbs in different languages. Uzbek and English proverbs were used in this chapter. In both languages, there are themes of patriotism, patience, good luck and bad luck, hard work, family, bravery, morals and education, and each serves only to share good things. Also, in the process of research, attention was paid to the meaning aspects of English and Uzbek proverbs.

References:

- 1.O'zbek xalq maqollari (Tuzuvchilar: T. Mirzayev,A. Musoqulov, B. Sarimsoqov; Masul muharrir: Sh.Turdimov. T.: Sharq, 2005. — 7-8 b.
- 2.Panos Karagiorgos. Greek and English Proverb // Cambridge Scholars Publishing Lady Stephenson Library. - Newcastle upon Tyne, UK., 2015.
- 3.Meider, W, Dundes, A.The Wisdom of Many: Essays on the Proverb, (Ed). – NewYork, Garland. 1995.
- 4.Brown H.D. Principles of language learning and teaching. - Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey. 1994.
- 5.Maxsudova M. Muloqot psixologiyasi // O 'quv qo'llanma. — T., 2006.

